

This paper is published at Journal of Signal Processing Systems

DOI: 10.1007/s11265-024-01920-z

Elham Shamsinejad, [Touraj BaniRostam](#), Mir Mohsen Pedram, Amir Masoud Rahmani (2024)

Anonymizing Big Data Streams Using In-memory Processing: A Novel Model Based on One-time Clustering

Abstract: Big data privacy preservation is a critical challenge for data mining and data analysis. Existing methods for anonymizing big data streams using k-anonymity algorithms may cause high data loss, low data quality, and identity disclosure. In this paper, we propose a novel model for anonymizing big data streams using in-memory processing. The model uses a Spark framework to parallelize the anonymization process and a one-time clustering algorithm to avoid multiple iterations and allocate the data to optimal clusters. We evaluate the performance and effectiveness of the model using a real-world dataset and compare it with three popular k-anonymity algorithms: CRUE, Mean-Shift, and DBSCAN. The results show that the model has the lowest data loss and the highest data quality for different data sizes and k-values. The model is scalable, robust, adaptable, and flexible. The model can provide better data for data mining and data analysis while protecting data privacy and preventing data disclosure.

Keywords: Big Data, Anonymity, In-Memory Processing, One-Time Clustering, Data Loss..

[Touraj BaniRostam](#) Contact Info:

☎ (437)-849-1498

✉ BaniRostam@gmail.com

[Touraj BaniRostam](#) Available at :

Google scholar:

https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=list_works&hl=en&hl=en&user=Igai5DsAAAAJ&pagesize=80&sortby=pubdate

Scopus: <https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=36496440300>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4632-6797>

ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Touraj-Banirostam?ev=hdr_xprf

Web of Science: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/MGU-4756-2025>

linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/tourajBaniRostam>

SSRN: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/cf_dev/AbsByAuth.cfm?per_id=7450086

ZENODO: <https://zenodo.org/me/uploads?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Bepress: <https://works.bepress.com/touraj-banirostam/>

Figshare: https://figshare.com/authors/Touraj_BaniRostam/20768990